

**THE LOG-BEHAVIOR OF SOME SEQUENCES RELATED TO THE
GENERALIZED LEONARDO NUMBERS**

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Abstract

Let $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ denote the generalized Leonardo sequence, where k is a fixed positive integer. In this paper, we discuss the log-behavior of some sequences related to $\mathcal{L}_{k,n}$. For example, we show that the sequences $\{\sqrt[n]{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}}\}_{n \geq 9}$ and $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}^n\}_{n \geq 3}$ are log-convex.

1. Introduction

The Leonardo sequence $\{Le_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ was introduced by Catarino and Borges [4]. This is sequence A001595 in the OEIS [14] and satisfies the recurrence relation

$$Le_{n+1} = Le_n + Le_{n-1} + 1 \quad (n \geq 1),$$

where $Le_0 = Le_1 = 1$. For a fixed positive integer k , Kuhapatanakul and Chobsorn [10] defined the generalized Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ by

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,n} = \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{k,n-2} + k \quad (n \geq 2), \tag{1}$$

where $\mathcal{L}_{k,0} = \mathcal{L}_{k,1} = 1$. It is clear that $\mathcal{L}_{1,n} = Le_n$. The value of $\mathcal{L}_{1,n}$ is the number of nodes in the Fibonacci tree of order n . The sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{2,n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is sequence A111314 in the OEIS [14]. Let $\{a_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ ($\{b_n\}_{n \geq 0}$) denote sequence A192746 (A192750) in the OEIS [14]. For $n \geq 1$, $\mathcal{L}_{3,n} = a_{n-1}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{4,n} = b_{n-1}$. The Leonardo numbers are related to the Fibonacci numbers. It is well known that the Fibonacci sequence $\{F_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfies the recurrence relation

$$F_{n+1} = F_n + F_{n-1} \quad (n \geq 1), \tag{2}$$

where $F_0 = 0$ and $F_1 = 1$. The Binet formula for $\{F_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is

$$F_n = \frac{\alpha^n - (-1)^n \alpha^{-n}}{\sqrt{5}},$$

where $\alpha = (1 + \sqrt{5})/2$. Catarino and Borges [4] proved that $Le_n = 2F_{n+1} - 1$ for $n \geq 0$. Kuhapatanakul and Chobsorn [10] showed that

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,n} = (k + 1)F_{n+1} - k, \quad (n \geq 0). \tag{3}$$

Recently, more properties of Leonardo numbers have been studied (see for instance [1, 4, 5, 10, 11, 13, 16]).

The purpose of this paper is to discuss the log-behavior of some sequences involving $\mathcal{L}_{k,n}$. Now we recall some definitions involved in this paper. A positive sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is said to be *log-convex* (*log-concave*) if $z_n^2 \leq z_{n-1}z_{n+1}$ ($z_n^2 \geq z_{n-1}z_{n+1}$) for each $n \geq 1$. A log-convex sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is said to be *log-balanced* if $\{z_n/n!\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-concave (Došlić [7] gave this definition). It is evident that a sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-convex (log-concave) if and only if its quotient sequence $\{z_{n+1}/z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is nondecreasing (nonincreasing) and a log-convex sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-balanced if and only if $\{z_{n+1}/((n + 1)z_n)\}_{n \geq 0}$ is nonincreasing. Log-behavior of sequences is not only a fertile source for inequalities, but also plays an important role in many subjects (see for instance [2, 3, 9, 6, 8, 12, 15]). Hence the log-behavior of sequences deserves to be studied. In the next section, we investigate the log-behavior of a series of sequences related to $\mathcal{L}_{k,n}$.

2. The Log-Behavior of Some Sequences Related to the Generalized Leonardo Numbers

In what follows, the following lemmas will be used.

Lemma 1. ([17]) *Let $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a positive sequence of real numbers defined by the following recurrence relation*

$$z_n = c_1z_{n-1} - c_2z_{n-2} - \cdots - c_kz_{n-k}, \quad n \geq k,$$

where $k \geq 2$, $c_1 > 0$, $c_j \geq 0$ ($2 \leq j \leq k$). If $\{z_0, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_k, z_{k+1}\}$ is log-concave (log-convex), the sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-concave (log-convex).

Lemma 2. *Let $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a positive sequence defined by the recurrence relation*

$$z_{n+1} = c_1z_n - c_2z_{n-2}, \quad n \geq 2, \tag{4}$$

where $c_1 > 0$ and $c_2 \geq 0$ are constants. For $n \geq 0$, let $x_n = z_{n+1}/z_n$. If there exists a nonnegative integer n_0 such that $\{1/z_{n_0}, 1/z_{n_0+1}, 1/z_{n_0+2}, 1/z_{n_0+3}\}$ is log-balanced and $c_1x_nx_{n+1} - 3c_2 \geq 0$ for $n \geq n_0$, then the sequence $\{1/z_n\}_{n \geq n_0}$ is log-balanced.

Proof. Since $\{1/z_{n_0}, 1/z_{n_0+1}, 1/z_{n_0+2}, 1/z_{n_0+3}\}$ is log-balanced, $\{z_j\}_{n_0 \leq j \leq n_0+3}$ is log-concave. It follows from Lemma 1 that $\{z_n\}_{n \geq n_0}$ is log-concave. Then $\{1/z_n\}_{n \geq n_0}$

is log-convex. For $n \geq 0$, let $x_n = z_{n+1}/z_n$. It follows from (4) that

$$x_n = c_1 - \frac{c_2}{x_{n-2}x_{n-1}}, \quad n \geq 2. \tag{5}$$

In order to prove that $\{1/z_n\}_{n \geq n_0}$ is log-balanced, we need to show that $\{1/((n+1)x_n)\}_{n \geq n_0}$ is decreasing. Now we prove by induction that $\{(n+1)x_n\}_{n \geq n_0}$ is increasing. Since $\{1/z_j\}_{n_0 \leq j \leq n_0+3}$ is log-balanced, $(j+2)x_{j+1} \geq (j+1)x_j$ for $n_0 \leq j \leq n_0+2$. Assume that $(j+2)x_{j+1} \geq (j+1)x_j$ for $j \geq n_0+2$. It follows from (5) that

$$(j+3)x_{j+2} - (j+2)x_{j+1} = c_1 + \frac{c_2[(j+2)x_{j+1} - (j+3)x_{j-1}]}{x_{j-1}x_jx_{j+1}}.$$

It follows from $(j+2)x_{j+1} \geq (j+1)x_j \geq jx_{j-1}$ for $j \geq n_0+2$ that

$$(j+3)x_{j+2} - (j+2)x_{j+1} \geq c_1 - \frac{3c_2}{x_jx_{j+1}} = \frac{c_1x_jx_{j+1} - 3c_2}{x_jx_{j+1}} \geq 0.$$

Hence $\{(n+1)x_n\}_{n \geq n_0}$ is increasing. Naturally, $\{1/((n+1)x_n)\}_{n \geq n_0}$ is decreasing. □

Now we give the main results of this paper.

Theorem 1. *For the generalized Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 0}$, $\{1/\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-balanced.*

Proof. It follows from (1) that

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} = 2\mathcal{L}_{k,n} - \mathcal{L}_{k,n-2}, \quad n \geq 2.$$

Clearly, $c_1 = 2$ and $c_2 = 1$. By means of (3), we obtain

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,3} = 2k + 3, \quad \mathcal{L}_{k,4} = 4k + 5, \quad \mathcal{L}_{k,5} = 7k + 8, \quad \mathcal{L}_{k,6} = 12k + 13.$$

We observe that $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,j}\}_{3 \leq j \leq 6}$ is log-concave. Thus, the sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-concave by Lemma 1. It is clear that $\{1/\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-convex. Since $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-concave and

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}} = \alpha,$$

we have

$$\alpha \leq x_j \leq x_3 = \frac{4k+5}{2k+3} < 2 \quad (j \geq 3). \tag{6}$$

By applying (6), we derive $c_1x_nx_{n+1} - 3c_2 = 2x_nx_{n+1} - 3 \geq 2\alpha - 3 > 0$ for $n \geq 3$. On the other hand, we find that $\{1/z_3, 1/z_4, 1/z_5, 1/z_6\}$ is log-balanced. It follows from Lemma 2 that the sequence $\{1/\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-balanced. □

Theorem 2. For the generalized Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 0}$, let $R_n = \sum_{i=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{k,i}$ ($n \geq 0$). The sequence $\{R_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-concave.

Proof. For $n \geq 0$, Kuhapatanakul and Chobsorn [10] proved that

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{k,i} = \mathcal{L}_{k,n+2} - k(n+1) - 1. \tag{7}$$

It follows from (7) and (3) that

$$\begin{aligned} R_n^2 - R_{n-1}R_{n+1} &= [(k+1)(F_{n+3} - 1) - k(n+1)]^2 \\ &\quad - [(k+1)(F_{n+2} - 1) - kn][(k+1)(F_{n+4} - 1) - k(n+2)] \\ &= (k+1)^2[(F_{n+3} - 1)^2 - (F_{n+2} - 1)(F_{n+4} - 1)] + k^2 \\ &\quad + k(k+1)[n(F_{n+2} + F_{n+4} - 2F_{n+3}) + 2F_{n+2} - 2F_{n+3}]. \end{aligned}$$

For the Fibonacci sequence $\{F_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, there is an identity

$$F_n F_{n+2} - F_{n+1}^2 = (-1)^{n+1}. \tag{8}$$

Using (8) and (2), we have

$$R_n^2 - R_{n-1}R_{n+1} = (k+1)^2[F_n + (-1)^n] + k(k+1)(nF_n - 2F_{n+1}) + k^2.$$

We observe that $R_j^2 - R_{j-1}R_{j+1} > 0$ for $1 \leq j \leq 3$. For $n \geq 4$,

$$R_n^2 - R_{n-1}R_{n+1} \geq k(k+1)(4F_n - 2F_{n+1}) + k^2 = 2k(k+1)F_{n-2} + k^2 > 0.$$

Hence $\{R_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-concave. □

Theorem 3. For the generalized Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 0}$, $\{\sqrt[n]{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is log-convex.

Proof. It is clear that $\{\sqrt[n]{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is log-convex if and only if

$$2(n^2 - 1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n} - n(n+1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} - n(n-1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} \leq 0 \quad (n \geq 10).$$

For $n \geq 10$, put

$$S_n = 2(n^2 - 1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n} - n(n+1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} - n(n-1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}$$

and

$$T_n = \frac{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}^3 \mathcal{L}_{k,n+2}}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}^3}.$$

It is evident that

$$S_n - S_{n+1} = n(n+1) \ln T_n.$$

Owing to (3), (8), and (2),

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,n}^2 - \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} = (-1)^n(k+1)^2 + k(k+1)F_{n-2}. \tag{9}$$

This leads to

$$T_n = \frac{\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} + k(k+1)F_{n-2} + (-1)^n(k+1)^2}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+2} + k(k+1)F_{n-1} + (-1)^{n+1}(k+1)^2} \cdot \frac{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+2}}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}}.$$

For $j \geq 0$, set $x_j = \mathcal{L}_{k,j+1}/\mathcal{L}_{k,j}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} T_n &= \frac{\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} + k(k+1)F_{n-2} + (-1)^n(k+1)^2}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+2} + k(k+1)F_{n-1} + (-1)^{n+1}(k+1)^2} \cdot x_{n-1}x_{n+1} \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+2} + k(k+1)x_{n-1}x_{n+1}F_{n-2} + (-1)^n(k+1)^2x_{n-1}x_{n+1}}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+2} + k(k+1)F_{n-1} + (-1)^{n+1}(k+1)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Now we prove that $T_n \geq 1$ for $n \geq 10$. When $n \geq 4$,

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+2} + k(k+1)x_{n-1}x_{n+1}F_{n-2} + (-1)^n(k+1)^2x_{n-1}x_{n+1} > 0$$

and

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\mathcal{L}_{k,n+2} + k(k+1)F_{n-1} + (-1)^{n+1}(k+1)^2 > 0$$

hold. For $n \geq 10$, let

$$U_n = k(k+1)(x_{n-1}x_{n+1}F_{n-2} - F_{n-1}) + (-1)^n(k+1)^2(x_{n-1}x_{n+1} + 1).$$

It is obvious that $T_n \geq 1$ if and only if $U_n \geq 0$. We note that

$$U_n \geq k(k+1)(x_{n-1}x_{n+1}F_{n-2} - F_{n-1}) - (k+1)^2(x_{n-1}x_{n+1} + 1).$$

By using (6), we get

$$\begin{aligned} U_n &\geq k(k+1)(\alpha^2F_{n-2} - F_{n-1}) - 5(k+1)^2 \\ &\geq k(k+1)\left(\frac{5}{2}F_{n-2} - F_{n-1}\right) - 5(k+1)^2. \end{aligned}$$

By using (2), we have

$$U_n \geq k(k+1)\left(\frac{1}{2}F_{n-2} + F_{n-4}\right) - 5(k+1)^2 > 0 \quad (n \geq 10).$$

Naturally, $T_n \geq 1$ for each $n \geq 10$. Thus the sequence $\{S_n\}_{n \geq 10}$ is decreasing. We observe that

$$\begin{aligned} S_{10} &= 198 \ln(88k + 89) - 110 \ln(54k + 55) - 90 \ln(143k + 144) \\ &= 110 \ln\left(\frac{88k + 89}{54k + 55}\right) - 90 \ln\left(\frac{143k + 144}{88k + 89}\right) - 2 \ln(88k + 89) \\ &\leq 110 \ln \frac{44}{27} - 90 \ln \frac{287}{177} - 2 \ln 177 < 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $2(n^2 - 1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n} - n(n + 1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} - n(n - 1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} \leq 0$ holds for $n \geq 10$. □

Theorem 4. For the generalized Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 0}$, there exists a positive integer $n_k \geq \max\{9, (1 + \sqrt{64k - 7})/4\}$ such that $\{\sqrt[n]{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}}\}_{n \geq n_k}$ is log-balanced.

Proof. For $n \geq 0$, let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}_n &= n(n+1)(n+2) \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n+1}\right) + 2n(n+2) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} - (n+1)(n+2) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n} \\ &\quad - n(n+1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n+2}. \end{aligned}$$

It is clear that $\{\sqrt[n]{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}/n!}\}_{n \geq n_k}$ is log-concave if and only if $\mathcal{U}_n \geq 0$ for $n \geq n_k$. For $n \geq 0$, put $x_n = \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}/\mathcal{L}_{k,n}$. We note that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}_n &= n(n+1)(n+2) \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n+1}\right) + 2n(n+2) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} - (n+1)(n+2) \ln \frac{\mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}}{x_n} \\ &\quad - n(n+1) \ln(x_{n+1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}) \\ &= n(n+1)(n+2) \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n+1}\right) - 2 \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} + (n+1)^2 \ln \frac{x_n}{x_{n+1}} \\ &\quad + (n+1) \ln(x_n x_{n+1}) \\ &= n(n+1)(n+2) \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n+1}\right) - 2 \ln(x_3 \cdots x_n \mathcal{L}_{k,3}) + (n+1)^2 \ln \frac{x_n}{x_{n+1}} \\ &\quad + (n+1) \ln(x_n x_{n+1}). \end{aligned}$$

Since $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-concave, $x_{n-1}/x_n \geq 1$ for $n \geq 4$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}_n &\geq n(n+1)(n+2) \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n+1}\right) - 2 \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,3} - 2(n-2) \ln x_3 + (n+1) \ln(x_n x_{n+1}) \\ &= n(n+1)(n+2) \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{n+1}\right) - 2 \ln(2k+3) - 2(n-2) \ln \left(1 + \frac{2k+2}{2k+3}\right) \\ &\quad + (n+1) \ln(x_n x_{n+1}). \end{aligned}$$

By the inequality

$$\frac{t}{1+t} < \ln(1+t) < t \quad (t > 0) \tag{10}$$

and (6), we obtain

$$\mathcal{U}_n \geq n^2 + n - 2(2k+2) - \frac{2(n-2)(2k+2)}{2k+3} + 2(n+1) \ln \alpha.$$

It is clear that

$$\mathcal{U}_n \geq n^2 + n - 2(2k+2) - 2(n-2) + \frac{n+1}{2} \geq 0 \quad \left(n \geq \frac{1 + \sqrt{64k - 7}}{4}\right).$$

On the other hand, the sequence $\{\sqrt[n]{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is log-convex. Then there exists a positive integer $n_k \geq \max\{9, (1 + \sqrt{64k - 7})/4\}$ such that $\{\sqrt[n]{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}}\}_{n \geq n_k}$ is log-balanced. \square

Theorem 5. For the generalized Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 0}$, $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}^n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-convex.

Proof. It is clear that $\mathcal{L}_{k,n}^{2n} - \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1}^{n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}^{n+1} \leq 0$ ($n \geq 4$) is equivalent to

$$2n \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n} - (n-1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} - (n+1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} \leq 0 \quad (n \geq 4).$$

For $n \geq 0$, set $x_n = \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}/\mathcal{L}_{k,n}$ and

$$V_n = 2n \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n} - (n-1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} - (n+1) \ln \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} \quad (n \geq 4).$$

It is evident that

$$V_n = n \ln \frac{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}^2}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}} - \ln x_{n-1} - \ln x_n.$$

By (9), we have

$$V_n = n \ln \frac{\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} + (-1)^n (k+1)^2 + k(k+1)F_{n-2}}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}} - \ln x_{n-1} - \ln x_n.$$

For $n \geq 4$, it follows from (10) and (6) that

$$\begin{aligned} V_n &\leq \frac{(-1)^n (k+1)^2 n + nk(k+1)F_{n-2}}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}} - 2 \ln \alpha \\ &< \frac{(k+1)^2 n + nk(k+1)F_{n-2} - \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}}{\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

For convenience, let

$$W_n = (k+1)^2 n + nk(k+1)F_{n-2} - \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1} \quad (n \geq 4).$$

Then $V_n < W_n/(\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} \mathcal{L}_{k,n+1})$. One can prove by induction that

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,j} > 2kj \quad (j \geq 6). \tag{11}$$

For $n \geq 5$, it follows from (11) that

$$W_n < (k+1)^2 n + nk(k+1)F_{n-2} - k(n+1)\mathcal{L}_{k,n-1}.$$

By using (3) and (2), we derive

$$\begin{aligned} W_n &< (k+1)^2 n + nk(k+1)F_{n-2} - k(n+1)[(k+1)F_n - k] \\ &= (k+1)^2 n + k^2(n+1) - nk(k+1)F_{n-1} - k(k+1)F_n \\ &< 0 \quad (n \geq 5). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $V_n < 0$ for $n \geq 5$. On the other hand, we find that $V_4 < 0$. Hence the sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}^n\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-convex. \square

3. Conclusions

For the generalized Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 0}$, we discussed the log-behavior of some sequences involving $\mathcal{L}_{k,n}$ in this paper. We mainly proved that $\{1/\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n \geq 3}$ is log-balanced and $\{\sqrt[n]{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}}\}_{n \geq 9}$ and $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}^n\}_{n \geq 3}$ are log-convex. Let $\{f_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a positive sequence. The future work is to study the log-behavior of $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}^{f_n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ under some conditions.

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